

The role of luxury value perception in consumer behavior towards counterfeit luxury goods: the case of Moroccan consumers

Kenza BOUDERBALA IDRISSE¹, Salima JAZI², Siham MOURAD³

¹ ENCG Settat, Hassan 1st University, Morocco

²ENCG Settat, Hassan 1st University, Morocco

³ ISCAE Group, Casablanca, Morocco

Abstract: Counterfeiting is a growing industry all over the world and Morocco is not an exception, as counterfeiting is widely spread due mainly to the absence of strict regulation in this matter.

The researches about the consumer's behavior towards luxury counterfeit are very rare in Moroccan context. Our study attempts to contribute to this field by studying the effect of luxury value perception and attitude toward counterfeiting on consumer's behavior toward luxury counterfeit. Concerning the methodological facet, we have conducted a quantitative study with a sample of 210 Moroccan consumers of luxury counterfeit products. We have also performed a PLS model that includes word-of-mouth (WoM) and purchase intention as consumer's behavior explanatory variables. We concluded that the luxury value perception influences the WoM that influences the purchase intention of counterfeit, whereas attitude toward counterfeiting has no significant effect. From a managerial perspective, brand managers should focus promoting their luxury brand value instead of fighting counterfeiting in a context where counterfeiting is fairly common

Key Words: Counterfeiting, Luxury value perception, Purchase intention, Word-of-mouth (WoM), PLS model.

1. INTRODUCTION

Moroccan people have always been interested and passionate by luxury fashion goods. According to a marketing study published in 2008 by Paris Tourist Office, Moroccans are the 10th best foreign customers of Parisian luxury shops.

Whilst most of the Moroccan luxury customers used to do their luxury shopping abroad, the things have been changed since 2016 with the opening of "Morocco mall" and the various luxury brands in Casablanca and Rabat. Consequently, the sector has been growing steadily from one year to another, and recorded a double-digit growth in 2018

Paradoxically, in Morocco, counterfeiting represents a real plague. The country is even one of the key players in the global counterfeiting market. Indeed, in 2016 it was ranked 11th exporter and 6th producer of counterfeit and pirated products by the OCDE (Organization for Cooperation and Economic Development).

This phenomenon represents a real loss for the Moroccan economy, since it generates, according to L'OMPIC (l'Office Nationale de la propriété industrielle et commerciale), an annual tax loss of nearly 1 billion and the loss or change in the informal of 30,000 jobs. Furthermore, and according to the same source; in 2016 counterfeiting on the Moroccan market is estimated between 6 and 12 MMDHS or 0.7% to 1.3% of the PIB. The Administration of Customs and Indirect Taxes (ADII) for its part announced, in its 2015 activity report, the seizure of 1.2 million counterfeit articles for a total value of 140 million dirhams (value increased by more than 32% compared to 2014).

However, the impact of counterfeiting on Moroccan customer behavior is less known as there is a lack in researches about the consumer behavior of original and counterfeit luxury products in Morocco.

The main contribution of this article is to study the counterfeiting buying behavior of Moroccan consumers based on their attitude towards counterfeit and their luxury value perception.

The detailed research objectives are to:

- Describe how the relation of Moroccan consumer with counterfeit of luxury can explain their purchase behavior by demonstrating whether or not the attitude towards counterfeit impacts the word-of-mouth (WoM) and the purchase intention.
- Describe how the relation of Moroccan with Luxury can explain the purchase behavior by explaining how luxury value perception impacts the WoM and the intention to buy counterfeit products.
- Develop a conceptual model explaining the relationship between Moroccan's luxury value perception, their attitude towards counterfeit, WoM and purchase intention of counterfeit luxury.

As "luxury" is a complex construct, we will start our literature review by defining the term "luxury" as well as presenting a state of art concerning "luxury value perception" which is an interesting and under studied concept.

Then, we will define "counterfeit" and mention the main findings related to "attitude toward counterfeit".

2. LITTERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Defining the Luxury Concept

The word "luxury" is not easy to define, as it has not one agreed definition. We will mention here a summary of the most important definitions proposed by the main authors in this field.

To start by the origin of the word "luxury", it comes from the Latin "luxus" (both adjective and noun), which is originally a term of agricultural vocabulary. According to the Etymological Cambridge Dictionary, "luxury" is defined as "something expensive that is pleasant to have but is not necessary"

Traditionally, a luxury product can be defined as a product that the simple fact of using or displaying brings prestige to the owner, apart from any functional utility (Grossman and Shapiro, 1988b). According to Allerès (1992), "luxury is above all a notion of dream accompanied by something functional". According to Roux (1991), "The luxury brand is characterized by an imaginary or social symbolic added value that differentiates it from others. "The luxury brand thus corresponds to the symbolic needs that the consumer may feel (as opposed to functional or variety needs) ".

Luxury touches various sectors such as perfumes, cosmetics, jewelry, automobiles, watches, sewing, tableware, leather, furs, decoration, furnishing, hospitality, gastronomy.... Within each of these sectors, it is possible to distinguish 3 types of luxury universe or different markets for this type of product (Allerès, 1997):

- The inaccessible luxury: models, lifestyle of the class and distinctive.
- Intermediate luxury: reproduction of models by an intermediate class.
- Affordable Luxury: Series Objects for a Middle Class.

As can be seen, these definitions refer to various notions: uselessness, pleasure and desire, but also refinement, cost, scarcity or exception.

2.2 Luxury value perception: state of art

Precedent researches demonstrated that customer behavior differs from a person to another depending on their susceptibility to interpersonal influence (Bushman 1993; Pantzalis 1995). In the context of luxury consumption, several researches have tried to understand and explain the customer behavior and his motives to consume luxury goods. The most studied aspects are interpersonal aspects like snobbery and conspicuousness (Leibenstein 1950; Mason 1992), personal aspects such as

hedonist and perfectionist motives (Dubois and Laurent 1994) as well as situational conditions such as economic, societal, political factors (Vigneron and Johnson 1999, 2004). However, the customer decision to buy a luxury brand is much more complicated to be explained only by these aspects. The customer perceived value of a luxury brand, defined as "a consumer's overall assessment of the utility of a product based on perceptions of what is received and what is given" (Zeithaml, 1988, p. 14) based on "an interactive relativistic consumption preference experience" (Holbrook, 1994, p. 27), should be taken in consideration when studying the customer behavior of luxury goods. Indeed, the perception of a value of a luxury brand may differ from a customer to another for the same brand based on some variables that have been developed by different researchers throughout the years.

Vigneron and Johnson (2004) developed a "brand luxury index" proposing that luxury consumer's decision-making process can be explained by five main factors that form a semantic network. Personal perceptions which are perceived extended self and perceived hedonism, non-personal perceptions which are perceived conspicuousness, perceived uniqueness, perceived quality). The authors reviewed the latent structure of the interrelations among the primary meanings of the luxury concept that inspire the decision-making process that occurs when assessing luxury brands.

Wiedmann, Hennigs and Siebels (2009), inspired by the work of Vigneron and Johnson (2004) proposed a multidimensional model that synthesizes all relevant cognitive and emotional value dimensions in a what really adds luxury value in the consumer's perception through the existence of four latent luxury value dimensions:

- Financial Dimension of Luxury Value Perception (price value)
- Functional Dimension of Luxury Value Perception (usability value, quality value, uniqueness value)
- Individual Dimension of Luxury Value Perception (self-identity value, hedonic value and materialistic value)
- Social Dimension of Luxury Value Perception (conspicuous value, prestige value)

The above-mentioned dimensions highlight several important indicators of luxury value perception. First, luxury value perception has a strong financial dimension as high price and functionality of a product are related with the overall price perception. Then, the personal dimension is also very important as it confirms that the experience and pleasure are determinant of luxury value perception and last but not least, the social dimension takes into account both self and others while acquiring luxury goods.

Berthon et al. (2009) conceptualized the value of luxury goods into three distinct dimensions: the objective (material), the subjective (individual) and the collective (social). On the other hand, Shukla and al. (2012) provided empirical support to luxury value perceptions in cross-national context using five distinct parameters; The dimensions include self-directed symbolic/expressive value, other-directed symbolic/expressive value,

experiential/hedonic value, utilitarian/functional value and cost/sacrifice value.

In the literature, the relation between luxury value and purchase intention of luxury product has been proven (Shukla et al 2012). The value of our research is to demonstrate whether or not there is a relation between luxury value perception and the purchase intention of counterfeit luxury products through the mediating effect of WoM, which we will try to confirm through our empirical study.

In fact, WoM has been acknowledged as a major determinant on what people know, feel and do (Buttle, 1998). It is more important than advertising in the purchase decision (Shelt, 1971). Then, we can assess the following hypothesis:

H1: Luxury value perception positively affects word-of-mouth

H2: Word-of-mouth positively affects purchase intention

2.3 Counterfeit definition

According to the National Anti-Counterfeiting Committee (CNAC), counterfeiting is defined as the reproduction, imitation or use of a trademark of a design, a patent, a software of a copyright or a plant variety without the authorization of its author. This rather legal definition of counterfeiting brings out two types of counterfeiting; the first type is to exactly reproduce the characteristics of the product in order to make the consumer believe that he buys an original. The second type is to imitate a product or its distinctive signs (logo, design, name...).

As per the World Trade Organization (WTO), counterfeiting is an «Unauthorized representation of a registered trademark carried on goods identical or similar to goods for which the trademark is registered, with a view to deceiving the purchaser into believing that he/she is buying the original goods».

Several authors have suggested more or less similar or complementary definitions of counterfeiting. Kapferer (1995) and Phillips (2005) have proposed a definition that highlights the illegal nature of counterfeiting: "a counterfeit good refers to any unauthorized product that infringes intellectual property (trademark, patent, or copyright)".

Other researchers have suggested definitions of counterfeiting that are complementary to the previous ones. Thus Kay (1990) defines counterfeiting as the production of copies with the same packaging, trade name, and label as the original mark to make the consumer believe that he is buying the original product.

Bloch, Bush, and Campbell (1993) defined counterfeiting as the unauthorized copying of products protected by trademarks or copyrights.

In the work of Cordell, Wongtada and Kieschnick (1996), product counterfeiting is defined as any manufacturing of goods whose special features are protected with intellectual property rights.

For more recent definitions, we mention McCarthy (2004) who defines counterfeit as: "the act of producing or selling a product intentionally and intentionally containing

the reproduction of the original article ». The counterfeit article is then identical or hardly distinguishable from the original article.

Eisend and Schuchert-Guler (2006) consider that counterfeiting is when a product with a recognized brand value on the market is copied by another product that becomes difficult to distinguish between the two. The copied product is then presented at a lower price as if it were the original.

2.4 Attitude towards counterfeiting

Attitude is defined as the consumer's opinion and beliefs about counterfeiting exterior of any purchasing situation (André Le Roux et al., 2006).

The attitude towards counterfeiting must be distinguished from the attitude towards the purchase of counterfeit products according to the distinction made by Fishbein and Ajzen (Fishbein, 1967, Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975). Indeed, an individual can have a positive attitude towards a concept or idea in general, without being willing to engage in behavior related to this concept.

The attitude of the consumer towards counterfeit products has been the subject of particular attention by researchers. André le Roux et al, (2006) studied the determinants of the attitude towards counterfeiting. For that, the authors considered the traditional conception of the attitude as one-dimensional concept determined by a set of determinants. They suggested a synthetic classification of determinants (explanatory variables of consumer behavior in this domain) taken from the literature. Economic determinants that correspond to the different levels of economic risk linked to the purchase of counterfeit products (loss of jobs, deficit in the balance of foreign trade, etc.). Individual determinants (attitude to market practices, ethics and perceived risk). Product related determinants (price, quality). Their study revealed eleven determinants of attitude that were used as explanatory variables of consumer attitudes and behavior with regard to counterfeiting, which are: psychosocial risk, playfulness, revenge on large groups, economic risk for the brand, perceived quality, economic risk for the company, ethical-moral dimension, physical risk, legal risk, abusive price, windfall price, ethical dimension - origin.

Another interesting study in an Australian context (Phau, Sequeira and Dix, 2009) looked at personality factors and their effect on consumers' attitudes towards counterfeits and their willingness to buy consciously counterfeit luxury brands (the study concerns luxury brands with strong involvement). Two new variables (Product Performance and Functional Life) were included to study their influence on consumers' willingness to buy counterfeit goods. The results of the study showed that integrity is the only factor influencing attitudes towards counterfeits. The lifecycle of a counterfeit luxury brand significantly influences consumers' willingness to buy. However, attitude and personality factors do not influence consumers' willingness to purchase the counterfeit luxury brand.

Kremer, Le Roux, Muller, Viot (2009), have tried to study the determinants of the attitude towards counterfeiting but

this time in different cultural contexts (France, Switzerland, Egypt, Morocco, Lebanon and Mauritius). The attitude towards counterfeiting has been studied by considering its three components: attitude towards counterfeiting in general, attitude towards the purchase of counterfeit products, intention to purchase counterfeit products. The results were as follows: The explanatory dimensions of the attitude towards counterfeiting in general and towards the purchase of counterfeit products are similar in the two samples: Ludic dimension and origin of the products. However, there are some differences: The buying intention of the European respondents is influenced by the physical risk whereas it is not the case for the non-European respondents.

A number of research on counterfeiting has been done in the Chinese market as it is among the most affected market by counterfeiting. Indeed, 20% of products sold on the Chinese market are counterfeit products (Alcock et al., 2003, Bian and Veloutsou, 2007). In 2009, Ian Phau and Min Teah studied how social factors and personality influence the attitudes of Chinese consumers towards counterfeit luxury brands and how these two sets of variables influence purchase intention. They provide a profile of buyers and non-buyers of counterfeit luxury brands. The study shows that consumer attitudes towards counterfeit luxury brand play an important role in customer purchase intention. Consumers are more influenced by the perceptions of counterfeit luxury brands than by ethical and legal considerations. "Integrity" and "consumption status" are the most significant factors that influence consumers' attitudes and purchase intentions. To be noted that buyers have more positive views on counterfeits in terms of quality, reliability and functionality than non-buyers, which is consistent with previous research (eg Wee et al., 1995; Nia and Zaichkowsky 2000, Ang et al., 2001, Wang et al., 2005).

Using the Planned Behavior Theory (TPB) developed by Ajzen (1991), the decision to engage in a behavior is predicted by the intention to perform the behavior, which can be predicted by the attitude, subjective norms and perceived behavioral control

In our study, the TPB can explain perfectly the decision to buy a counterfeit; we will try to confirm through our empirical study that attitude towards counterfeit influence the intention to buy counterfeit product. In addition to the direct relation, we will test the relation with the mediating effect of the WoM:

H3 : Attitude toward counterfeiting positively affects word-of-mouth

H4 : Attitude toward counterfeiting positively affects purchase intention

In fact, our research model is defined as below:

Figure -1: Research model

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Sample and Data Collection Process

Using face-to-face questionnaires, we carried a quantitative study in Morocco, where both genuine and counterfeit luxury products are massively available. Indeed, according to the National Committee for the industrial property and against counterfeiting (CONPIAC), the Moroccan counterfeiting market has been estimated between 8 and 16 million dollars in 2012. The final sample has been chosen using a convenience sampling and led to a total of 210 Moroccan consumers that have consumed at least one counterfeited item during the last twelve months (only fashion wear and accessories: perfume, bag, jewel, watch, etc.). The data collection lasted three months from September to November 2019.

3.2 Measures

This research used five-point Likert scales. Luxury value perception was measured with the scale of Shukla & Purani, (2012) and attitude toward counterfeiting with the scale of Phau & Teah (2009). To measure counterfeit word-of-mouth, the scale of Harrison-Walker (2001) has been used. For purchase intention of counterfeit, the scale of Cronin et al. (2000) was applied.

4. Results and conclusions

4.1. Validity, Reliability and Adjustment Quality

A PLS approach has been selected because of its suitability to handle higher order latent constructs and violation of multivariate normality. More precisely, we relied on a consistent PLS approach which avoids inflated loadings and gives consistent structural path coefficients (Dijkstra and Henseler, 2015).

Furthermore, we used non-parametric bootstrapping with 5000 replications to obtain the standard errors of the estimates (Chin, 2010; Hair et al., 2014, 2012; Henseler et al., 2012, 2009).

First, the reliability and validity of each concept has been estimated. As shown on *table 1*, indicators of convergent validity and reliability are satisfied: the reliability is greater than 0.8 (except Attitude toward counterfeit greater than 0.6) and the convergent validity is equal to or greater than 0.5.

In order to assess discriminant validity, we relayed on heterotrait-monotrait (HTMT) criterion that is inferior to 0.85. The discriminant validity is then satisfied (Henseler et al., 2015).

Latent variable	Convergent validity (AVE: Average Variance Extracted)	Reliability (Dillon-Goldstein's Rho)
Luxury value perception	0.638	0.898
Attitude toward counterfeiting	0.567	0.659
Word-of-mouth	0.531	0.8
Purchase intention	0.477	0.848

Table1: Convergent Validity and Reliability Indices

	Attitude toward counterfeiting	Luxury value perception	Purchase intention
Luxury value perception	0.311		
Purchase intention	0.349	0.177	
Word-of-mouth	0.432	0.259	0.543

Table2 : Ratio Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT)

Then, we could assess the quality of the model. Following recent advices by Henseler and Sarstedt (2013), we have used the SRMR criteria. In our research, the SRMR (Standardized Root Mean Square Residual) value is **0.106**, which corresponds to an acceptable adjustment (Henseler et al., 2015). Once the adequacy of the model is verified, we have assessed the structural relationships among the model (see *Figure 1*).

Figure-2: PLS Structural Model

4.2. Hypothesis Testing

Our research aimed to study the effect of luxury value perception and attitude toward counterfeit on purchase intention with the mediating effect of the WoM. Based on the tested model (Figure 1), we have studied the effect of each latent variable by exploring the paths coefficients which describe direct dependencies among the set of latent variables.

The study demonstrates a positive influence of luxury value perception on word-of-mouth (path coefficient: +0.139 / sign<5%), and a positive effect of word-of-mouth on purchase intention (path coefficient: +0.447 / sign<1%). This leads to accept the hypotheses H1 and H2 and to confirm the direct effect of luxury value perception on WoM and its indirect effect on purchase intention. The more people have positive luxury value perception, the more they talk about their purchase and the more they re-purchase counterfeited products. Indeed, our sample of Moroccan consumers consider luxury counterfeit as valuable as luxury product and in fact a positive luxury value perception impacts positively the counterfeit WoM and the purchase intention of counterfeit luxury products.

Concerning attitude towards counterfeiting, our study was unable to demonstrate the effect of attitude toward counterfeiting on WoM or on purchase intention

(hypothesis H3 and H4 are rejected). It can be explained by the fact that attitude towards counterfeit plays no role in counterfeit purchase intention in Moroccan context. For Moroccans, counterfeit products play the same role than luxury items, so the attitude towards counterfeits does not impact their purchase consideration.

On the other hand, our model reveals a slightly weak predictive power for word-of-mouth ($R^2=13.5\%$), which can be explained by the fact that other excluded variables may affect this construct.

5. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

This investigation has as a start point, the lack of studies concerning luxury value perception in the context of counterfeiting. The first contribution of the study concerns the primordial role of luxury value perception in counterfeit purchase behavior. Then, we suggest a conceptualization that demonstrates that luxury value perception directly influences word-of-mouth and indirectly affects counterfeit luxury purchase. Concerning the second contribution, attitude toward counterfeits plays no role in counterfeit purchase intention. Surprisingly, Moroccan consumers do not take in consideration attitude toward counterfeiting as a criterion of their purchase intention.

From the managerial perspective, we suggest to Luxury Marketing Managers to counter counterfeiting by focusing on the luxury brand itself, its value, history and attributes instead on focusing on fighting the counterfeit, which take a lot of unnecessary effort. In fact, in emergent countries where counterfeits are available in the same way as legitimate products, marketers should focus on the real value of legitimate luxury brands.

They should choose the appropriate marketing tool and the appropriate argument to enhance luxury value perception, which may lead to more positive WoM. Increasing luxury value perception may be settled through: the price value (eg. Luxury item worth its price), the usage or quality value, (eg. Nothing can equal the quality of luxury item), the self-identity value, materialistic value, or conspicuous value (eg. luxury products are the only items that may create prestige value).

Concerning the limitations of this research, we can state that we have studied some variables that may explain WoM in the context of counterfeiting and have overlooked other factors such as personal variables (eg. personality), factors related to the product or the brand (eg. Attitude toward the brand) or factors related to the culture which may be very relevant in Moroccan context. Furthermore, the model reveals a slightly weak predictive power for the WoM ($R^2=13.5\%$) which proves that luxury value perception is not the only antecedent of WoM. It will be interesting to study the effect of other variables that may influence the WoM and the purchase intention. Moreover, we have limited the investigation to fashion wear and accessories while consumer's behavior toward counterfeiting can fluctuate depending on the category of the product or even the nature of the product.

Regarding research directions, it will be interesting to deepen the comprehension of attitude toward counterfeiting in Moroccan context: how does consumer

perceive counterfeit? What are the differences between counterfeit and legitimate items in Moroccan consumer's view?

Furthermore, it will be interesting to identify profiles of Moroccan consumers regarding their luxury value perception and their counterfeiting purchase behavior. A characterization with socio-demographic elements (eg. profession, matrimonial situation) or live styles will be necessary for brand managers to a better identification of these groups. The segmentation may also be applied to all consumers including consumers of legitimate luxury brands.

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Annex 1 : Study questionnaire

As our study occurs in Morocco and concern Moroccan customers, our questionnaire is edited in French as it's the common language in Morocco

Bonjour Mademoiselle, Madame, Monsieur,
Dans le cadre d'une recherche à caractère purement universitaire, nous nous intéressons à la réaction du consommateur marocain face à la contrefaçon de luxe. Nous désignons par contrefaçon, tout produit d'imitation identique au produit original. Dans le cadre de cette étude, nous nous limiterons exclusivement aux **vêtements et aux accessoires de luxe** (parfum, sac, bijou, montre, etc.).

Nous vous serions reconnaissants de bien vouloir répondre à ce questionnaire le plus **spontanément et sincèrement** possible. Il est important que vous **répondiez à toutes les questions**, même si celles-ci vous paraissent étranges ou répétitives.

Toutes les opinions nous intéressent, il n'y a donc **pas de bonnes ou de mauvaises réponses**. Seul votre avis personnel compte.

Aussi, les réponses sont **anonymes** et ne seront en aucun cas utilisées pour des fins commerciales. Merci d'avance pour votre collaboration.

Mémo enquêteur

Nom de l'enquêteur :

Numéro de l'observation :

Le répondant fait-il partie de la cible ?

- Pays de résidence : Maroc
- Nationalité : Marocaine
- Consommation d'une contrefaçon de marque de luxe
- L'article consommé est un vêtement ou un accessoire d'habillement

Partie 1 : Questions filtres

Afin de s'assurer que vous appartenez bien à la cible que l'on souhaite interroger, merci de répondre aux questions suivantes :

Q1- Quel est votre sexe ?

1- Femme ; 2- Homme

Q2- Dans quelle tranche d'âge vous situez-vous ?

1- Moins de 25 ans ; 2- [25-34] ; 3- [35-44] ; 4- [45-54] ; 5- [55-64] ; 6- [65-74] ; 7- Plus de 74 ans

Q3- Quel est votre dernier diplôme obtenu ?

1- Brevet ; 2- Baccalauréat ; 3- Bac + 2 (DEUG/BTS/DUT) ; 4- Bac + 3 / + 4 (Licence/Maîtrise) ; 5- Bac + 5 ou plus (Grande école/Master/Doctorat) ; 6- Aucun diplôme

Q4- Quelle est votre nationalité ?

1- Marocaine ; 2- Autre à préciser

Q5- Quel est votre pays de résidence principale ?

1- Maroc ; 2- Autre à préciser

Q6- Durant les 12 derniers mois, avez-vous consommé ou utilisé un vêtement ou un accessoire d'habillement,

1) Armani	11) Fendi	21) Louis Vuitton
2) Bulgari	12) Gucci	22) Prada
3) Burberry	13) Hermès	23) Roberto Cavalli / Just Cavalli
4) Cartier	14) Hugo Boss	24) Rolex
5) Cerruti	15) Jimmy Choo	25) Sonia Rykiel
6) Chanel	16) Kenzo	26) Versace
7) Chaumet	17) Marc Jacobs	27) Yves Saint Laurent
8) Chopard	18) Lancel	28) Autre marque de luxe à préciser
9) Dior	19) Lanvin	
10) Dolce & Gabbana	20) Longchamp	

y compris un parfum) d'une des marques de luxe suivantes ? De quel type de produit s'agissait-il ?

1-Vêtement (chemise, pantalon, etc.) ; 2-Chaussure ; 3- Accessoire d'habillement (lunette de soleil, chapeau, etc.) ; 4- Sac à main, portefeuille ou étui ; 5-Article de bijouterie (bracelet, bague, montre) ; 6-Parfum, cosmétique ; 7-Autre type de produit (hors vêtement et accessoire)

Q6bis- Durant les 12 derniers mois, avez-vous consommé ou utilisé une contrefaçon (uniquement vêtement ou un accessoire d'habillement, y compris un parfum) d'une des marques de luxe suivantes ? De quel type de produit s'agissait-il ?

1) Armani	11) Fendi	21) Louis Vuitton
2) Bulgari	12) Gucci	22) Prada
3) Burberry	13) Hermès	23) Roberto Cavalli / Just Cavalli
4) Cartier	14) Hugo Boss	24) Rolex
5) Cerruti	15) Jimmy Choo	25) Sonia Rykiel
6) Chanel	16) Kenzo	26) Versace
7) Chaumet	17) Marc Jacobs	27) Yves Saint Laurent
8) Chopard	18) Lancel	28) Autre marque de luxe à préciser
9) Dior	19) Lanvin	
10) Dolce & Gabbana	20) Longchamp	

1-Vêtement (chemise, pantalon, etc.) ; 2-Chaussure ; 3- Accessoire d'habillement (lunette de soleil, chapeau, etc.) ; 4- Sac à main, portefeuille ou étui ; 5-Article de bijouterie

(bracelet, bague, montre) ; 6-Parfum, cosmétique ; 7-Autre type de produit (hors vêtement et accessoire)

Q7- Parmi les contrefaçons de marques de luxe que vous avez consommées durant les douze derniers mois, quelle est celle qui a le plus de signification pour vous ?

- | | | |
|-------------|-----------------|------------------------------------|
| 1) Armani | 11) Fendi | 21) Louis Vuitton |
| 2) Bulgari | 12) Gucci | 22) Prada |
| 3) Burberry | 13) Hermès | 23) Roberto Cavalli / Just Cavalli |
| 4) Cartier | 14) Hugo Boss | 24) Rolex |
| 5) Cerruti | 15) Jimmy Choo | 25) Sonia Rykiel |
| 6) Chanel | 16) Kenzo | 26) Versace |
| 7) Chaumet | 17) Marc Jacobs | 27) Yves Saint Laurent |
| 8) Chopard | 18) Lancel | 28) Autre marque de luxe |
- à préciser
- 9) Dior 19) Lanvin
10) Dolce & Gabbana 20) Longchamp

Partie 2- Vous et le luxe

Q8- De façon générale, comment percevez-vous le luxe ?

- | |
|--|
| 1) J'achète souvent des produits de marque de luxe qui reflètent ma propre image |
| 2) J'aime posséder les nouveaux produits de luxe avant les autres |
| 3) Il est important pour moi de détenir de belles choses |
| 4) Selon moi, l'achat de produit de luxe est vraiment utile |
| 5) J'achète des produits de luxe pour gagner en statut social |
| 6) Je choisis la marque de luxe en fonction de comment je me vois et non de comment les autres me voient |
| 7) Je déteste les produits de luxe que tout le monde possède |
| 8) L'achat de produits de luxe me procure du plaisir |
| 9) Je considère mes achats de produits de luxe comme pratiques |
| 10) L'aspect unique des produits de luxe est important pour moi |
| 11) Je suis fortement attiré par les produits de luxe uniques. |
| 12) Les produits de luxe font de moi un « fashion leader » au lieu d'un « fashion suiveur » |
| 13) Dans mon esprit, un prix élevé est équivalent à une qualité élevée |
| 14) Les produits de luxe avec des prix élevés ont plus de signification pour moi |
| 15) Plus un article a un prix élevé, plus il est attirant à mes yeux |

1-Tout à fait d'accord ; 2-D'accord ; 3-Ni d'accord, ni pas d'accord ; 4-Pas d'accord ; 5-Pas du tout d'accord

Partie 3- Vous et la contrefaçon

Lors de cette partie, nous allons évoquer les articles contrefaits, c'est-à-dire les produits d'imitation qui ressemblent très fortement aux produits originaux.

Q9- De façon générale, que pensez-vous de la contrefaçon ? Veuillez nous indiquer votre degré d'accord avec les items suivants ?

- | |
|--|
| 1) La contrefaçon de marque de luxe est aussi fiable que la version originale |
| 2) L'achat de marque de luxe contrefaite enfreint la propriété industrielle |
| 3) La contrefaçon de marque de luxe a une qualité similaire à celle de la version originale |
| 4) L'achat de marque de luxe contrefaite nuit aux industries des produits de luxe |
| 5) La contrefaçon de marque de luxe procure les mêmes fonctionnalités que la version originale |
| 6) L'achat de contrefaçon de marque de luxe porte atteinte aux intérêts et aux droits des fabricants de produits originaux |
| 7) L'achat de marque de luxe contrefaite est illégal |
| 8) Je n'aime pas acheter un produit contrefait, parce que je ne sais pas par qui il a été fabriqué. |
| 9) Les produits contrefaits sont d'aussi bonne qualité que les produits originaux. |
| 10) Pour moi, les prix des produits originaux sont une arnaque. |
| 11) Je n'aime pas acheter un produit contrefait parce que je ne sais pas d'où il vient. |
| 12) La différence de qualité entre les produits originaux et les produits contrefaits est minime. |
| 13) A mon avis, les prix des produits originaux sont abusifs. |
| 14) Il n'y a pas de différence de qualité entre le produit contrefait et l'original. |
| 15) Pour moi, acheter un produit contrefait, c'est faire une bonne affaire. |
| 16) Les produits contrefaits sont aussi performants que les produits d'origine. |
| 17) Je pense qu'acheter un produit contrefait, c'est s'offrir la marque à moindre coût. |
| 18) Les produits contrefaits sont aussi fiables que les produits d'origine. |

1-Tout à fait d'accord ; 2-D'accord ; 3-Ni d'accord, ni pas d'accord ; 4-Pas d'accord ; 5-Pas du tout d'accord

Q10- En ayant à l'esprit la contrefaçon de marque..... (marque cochée dans Q7), diriez-vous que :

- | |
|---|
| 1) Il y a de fortes chances que j'utilise encore cette même contrefaçon |
| 2) Il est fort probable que je recommande cette contrefaçon à un ami |
| 3) Si ce choix était à refaire, j'achèterai la même contrefaçon |

1-Tout à fait d'accord ; 2-D'accord ; 3-Ni d'accord, ni pas d'accord ; 4-Pas d'accord ; 5-Pas du tout d'accord

Partie 4- Vous et votre achat

Lors de cette dernière partie, nous allons parler de vos achats de contrefaçon de façon générale

Q11- Que recherchez-vous lors de l'achat d'un produit contrefait -quelque soit sa nature-. Veuillez nous indiquer votre degré d'accord avec les affirmations

suivantes :

- | |
|--|
| 1) Je suis intéressé par les nouveaux produits ayant un statut |
| 2) Lorsque j'achète un produit, je gagne l'estime de mes amis |
| 3) J'achèterais un produit juste à cause de son statut |
| 4) Lorsque j'achète un produit, je gagne l'estime de ma famille |
| 5) Je pourrais payer plus pour un produit qui a un statut |
| 6) Lorsque je pense à acheter un produit, je deviens anxieux |
| 7) Le statut d'un produit est pertinent selon moi |
| 8) L'achat d'un produit me rend psychiquement inconfortable |
| 9) Pour moi, un produit a plus de valeur lorsqu'il a un attrait snob |
| 10) Le fait de penser à l'achat d'un produit m'entraîne dans une tension |

1-Tout à fait d'accord ; 2-D'accord ; 3-Ni d'accord, ni pas d'accord ; 4-Pas d'accord ; 5-Pas du tout d'accord

Q12- Comment vous décririez-vous ? Vous êtes généralement quelqu'un de :

- | |
|--|
| 1) Honnête, sincère |
| 2) Polit (courtois, avez de bonnes manières) |
| 3) Responsable (sérieux, fiable) |
| 4) Avez une bonne maîtrise de soi (réservé, auto-discipliné) |

1-Tout à fait d'accord ; 2-D'accord ; 3-Ni d'accord, ni pas d'accord ; 4-Pas d'accord ; 5-Pas du tout d'accord

Merci pour votre participation !